

SITE GS/SPHINX	DATE 7/16-17/79	AREA NE	SQUARE N3/W1	PAGE
 Feature No.	Coordinates:		Levels	
			Top: ≈ 10.65	Bottom: ≈ 10.52
	DIMENSIONS			
Diameter: 15 x 17 cm		Width:	Length:	Depth: ≈ 11 cm

Locus	Mat.	Color	Hard.	Consis.	Pottery	Inclusions			
①	CLAY	BROWN - TAN	compact	Fine	T / small sherd particle	Lm	particles throughout	Gp	interfaces w ②
						Gr		Char	
						Do			
					D	Ba			
						Al			
						Other			
②	GYPSUM	WHITE to BUFF	Compact but crumbly	Fine to grainy	T	Lm	frags and particles thruout	Gp	
						Gr		Char	spots
						Do			
					D	Ba			
						Al			
						Other			
③	Gypsum clay mix (?) "granite dust"	Light Grey	Fairly Packed but looser than ①, ②	Fine to powdery on drying	T	Lm	particles and small frags	Gp	inclusions - frags
						Gr	frags and fine particles	Char	
						Do	kerite chips		
					D	Ba			
						Al			
						Other			
3a	SAND (Quartz)	Brown to dark tan	Loose	grainy	T	Lm		Gp	
						Gr		Char	
						Do			
					D	Ba			
						Al			
						Other			
○					T	Lm		Gp	
						Gr		Char	
						Do			
					D	Ba			
						Al			
						Other			

PHOTOGRAPH	Color: Roll/	No./	B&W: Roll/	No./
			4	1 sub hole
DRAWN	Area Plan: 1:20 plotted	Feature Plan: 1:10 surface	Sections: 2, at 1:2	

REMARKS; INTERPRETATION: As shown in section, these - ①-②-③ interface or lens into each other - prob. laid in contemporaneous (?). Gypsum comes from upper outside top of hole to run in to hole under ①. Sides, bottom of hole show rust red discoloration. Small nat. sub hole at E edge of bottom as also case in Fh 14.